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An Assessment Of The Responses Of The Nigerian Government Toward Counterinsurgency And Counterterrorism And Its Impact On Education In Northeast Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria is one of the territories bedevilled by the activities of Boko Haram with adverse effect. Socially, educationally and economically as well. The group began its radical armed terror activities against all Western values and western systems of education particularly in North east Nigeria Attendance to school is dependent on the readiness of the child, encouragement from parents, provision of school materials and distance to school, above all; the security of the child. Boko Haram has become a threat of most parents and pupils in Yobe state. There are series of cases of bombing, burning of school and houses, abduction of school children lead to insecurity and unstable education in Yobe state as such parents no longer allow their children to attend schools regularly. This study therefore attempt to examined responses of Government and the impact of Boko Haram on social orientation and academic performance in affected secondary schools in Potiskum local government area of Yobe state and subsequently, means of converting the menace of such influence. (Way forward) shall be discuss to bring about the conducive environment for social and academic standard in the study area.

Keywords: Government, Boko-Haram Counterinsurgency, Education

INTRODUCTION

The nation Nigeria witnessed brutal confrontation and massive assault from terrorist group which is undoubtedly the most blood-thirsty and destructive, both in term of demonic brutality, mindless savagery and flagrant disobedience to the principles of peace and stability. Nigeria has witnessed counterinsurgency from this terrorist group called Boko Haram from 2009. They unleash terrorist group called Boko Haram from 2009. They unleash terror and fear in the minds of every Nigeria. There is

wanton destruction of government properties, bombing of churches, mosques and other public places, assassination of prominent individuals, burning of schools occasioned by sporadic shooting of innocent citizens (Abimbiola, & Adosote, 2012).

Insurgencies has been as old as civilization but became most prominent after the September 11, 2001 bombing of the United States by Al-Qaeda, the bombings were carried out on world trade centre which has adverse effects on the education and business activities or America and globally (Rogan, 2010). Other insurgent's activities were carried out by other groups such Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb of Algeria and Al-Shabaab of Somalia which also affects the education as well the economy of those countries. Insurgency as defined Oxford Advanced Learners' Dictionary (2008) is the rebellion or revolt, that's the state of being insurgent.

Boko Haram also known as the Jama'atu Ahlus Sunna Lidda Awati Wal- Jihad started as a small radical Sunni Islamic organization with preaching and a limited support from among the Sufi Islamic communities in the northeastern part of Nigeria, the anti-western ideology of the Book Haram terrorist group, earn it the concern about its potential relationship with other groups such as Sunni extremist or terrorist groups elsewhere, including al-Qaeda a swell as al-Qaeda affiliates such as al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM) in Algeria and Mali and Al-Shabaab in Somalia. There groups bomb schools, shopping malls; airports and business areas, thereby making education and business environment to collapse (Reuters, 2013).

In Hausa language, Book Haram means western education is an abomination or forbidden. This group was founded by a Nigerian named Mohammed Yusuf in the year 1995. As a Muslim sect that intends to abolish secular of government and establish Sharia law in Nigeria (Erne and Ibietan, 2012). It is an offshoot of a radical Islamic youth group which worshipped at the Alhaji Muhammad Ndimi mosque in Maiduguri, in the 1990s.

What today can be considered as a security monster could be traced to the teachings the Maitasine, Mohammed Marwa and a Muslim fundamentalist that rejected the impact of education system imposed by the British when they conquered the Sokoto caliphate in 1903 (Shettu, 2011). Like the members of the Ja'atu Ahlis Sunna Lidda Wati Wal-Jihad, which is the original name of Boko Haram meaning "people committed to the propagation of the prophet's teachings and Jihad" they strictly believed in the Qur'an phrase surah 4:11 "Anyone who is not governed by what Allah has revealed is among the transgressors. Hence members of these sects believed that it is 'Haram' or 'sinful' to embrace western education as it is not revealed by the prophet.

Abgbiboa, (2013) Education is worst hit by the Boko Haram activities. Apart from the fact that the fight is directly against western education which is widely practiced in Nigeria with schools established in every nook and cranny of the country, western education has remained the bedrock of human and capital developments in Nigeria. Education is under attack, as incidents of violence against students, teachers, union, schools and government officials are on the rise worldwide and in Nigeria particularly. Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria, deliberate threat against students, academics, teachers and educational facilities create barrier to accessing quality education (Abraka 2010). Education is a right, like the right to have proper food or roof over one's head. Education is not only a right bust passport to human development. It opens door and expands opportunities and freedom. It contributes to fostering peace, democracy and economic growth as well as improving health and reducing poverty. The current Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria is threatening to halt or even reverse this progress. Education is under attack in northern Nigeria particularly in Yobe State. These groups have carried out several attacks and issued threats to schools in the north in some of these attacks, teachers were liked or injured and structure razed. In September, 2013 a school of agriculture in Yobe state was attacked at night by the Boko Haram and more than sixty students were killed (Vanguard, 2013) also a secondary school in Mamudo town of Potiskum where more than thirty students were slaughtered, also a massacre of over four hundred people (male, female and children) at Potiskum cattle market and suicide bombing attack in Government Science and Technical College Potiskum which kills over sixty-three students and injured many among others. These are among the several attacks on schools by the Boko Haram. Longer-term impact of persistent

targeted violent attacks, including the destruction of schools and the killing of students, teachers and other education personnel, on education systems is very patchy

Statement of the Problem

Academic activities are disrupted intermittently as a result of sporadic attacks on education facilities. Government has had to shut down schools in order to forestall sudden attacks on them by insurgents. The Boko Haram attacks culminate in poor student's performance because learning is characterized by threat in the school environment of the north particularly in Potiskum local government area, Yobe state whereas it is an accomplished fact that learning thrives mostly in an environment devoid of threat. Etebu and James (2011) asserted that "any society characterized by any form of violence will not be conducive for any social interaction in form of teaching and learning". Similarly it has been noted that the threat of insecurity will constitute negative reinforcement due to the obvious fact that teaching and learning cannot occur successfully in an environment characterized by threat (Campbell, 2008). There are series of case bombing and burning of schools and houses in northern Nigeria particularly in Potiskum which include; suicide bombing attack in Government Science and Technical College of Potiskum which kills over twenty-six (26) students died in the attack and more than 81 students suffered minor to grievous injuries, Mamudo town of Potiskum where more than thirty students were slaughtered and school of Agriculture in Yobe state was attacked at night by the Boko Haram which more than sixty students were killed. Therefore, it is based on these facts that the researchers intends to investigate the impact of Boko Haram on social orientation and academic performance in affected secondary schools in Potiskum, Yobe state.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to investigate the responses of Government toward Boko Haran attacks and the impact of Boko Haram on social orientation and academic performance in affected secondary schools in Potiskum, Yobe State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Find out the impact of Boko Haram on social orientation well-being of students in some selected secondary schools in Potiskum, Yobe State.
2. Determine the impact of Boko Haram insurgency on the academic performance of students in the study area.
3. To proffered the ways forward by Government to tackle the attack of Boko Haram in the study area.

Research Questions

Three questions were formulated to guide the study.

- 1) What are the impacts of Boko Haram on social orientation well-being of students in some secondary school in Potiskum local government area of Yobe State?
- 2) What are the impacts of Boko Haram insurgency on the academic performance of students in the study area?
- 3) What are the ways forward by Government on tackling the attack of Boko Harams in the study area?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Insurgency: Is the rebellion against authority when those taking part in the rebellion are not recognized as belligerents. According to Powell and Abraham (2016), insurgency refers to a violent move by a person or group of persons to resist or oppose the enforcement of law or running of government or revolt against the constituted authority of the state or of taking part in insurrection. Insurgency as defined above becomes violate of the constitution's criminal law and the international treaty obligations of a nation in the following circumstance (Aminu, 2013).

Boko Haram: means western education is forbidden Insurgencies has been as old as civilization but became most prominent after the September 11 2001 bombings of the United States by Al-Qaeda. The bombing were carried out on world trade centre which has adverse effects on the business activities of America and globally (Rogan, 2017). Other insurgent's activities were carried out by other groups such Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Magreb of Algeria and Al-Shabaab of Somalia which also affects the business as well the economy of those countries.

Boko Haram started as a small radical Sunni Islamic organization with preaching and a limited support from among the Sufi Islamic communities in the north-eastern part of Nigeria, the anti-western ideology of the Boko Haram terrorist group, earn it the concern about its potential relationship with other groups such as Sunni extremist or terrorist groups elsewhere, including Al-Qaeda as well as Al-Qaeda affiliates such as Al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM) in Algeria and Mali and Al-Shabaab in Somalia. These groups bomb shopping malls; airports and business areas, thereby making business environment to collapse (Reuters, 2013).

Adike, (2012). The effective of Boko Haram attacks are not restricted to students in school and area that have actually been attacked, as an attack on one school or locality leads to fear that any school in the area might be attacked. Although, several research works have been carried out regarding the work of Boko Haram, little or nothing has been done concerning the extent to which the academic performance of secondary students of the north-eastern states has being affected. The research work attempts to look at the extent to which the sect has achieved its goal (Boko Haram) and the effect of this insurgency on students' academic performance so far.

According to Ovell (2011), peace in schools is essential for effective learning, good teacher relationship and peer adjustment. A democratic form of peace leads to a healthy classroom environment that in turn promotes respect for education and a desire for knowledge. Ovell quoted a number of studies which support this view.

Ways forward by Government to tackle the attack of Boko Haram and Towards Improving Academic Performance of Students

Of course, there are many viable solutions created by a mix of people passionate about changing the face of Nigeria's education. As such the following remedies can help schools identify areas that significantly impact students' performance and how they can use them to meet their individual school needs.

1. The state government should provide adequate security to prevent attacks on school buildings, teachers and student/pupils in the state.
2. The state government should renovate all schools damaged in the state as a result of violence and ensure that they are provided with adequate teaching staff and other resources in order that student's access to education can be resumed as quickly and smoothly as possible.
3. The federal government on their part should provide adequate support to the affected states government including Yobe state, to expeditiously rebuild and renovate all school buildings and facilities destroyed during the attacks.
4. The state government should provide all necessary support to all those, including teachers and students, who have been affected by violence in northeast Nigeria. This should include rehabilitation and resettlement for those who have been forced to flee the violence.
5. The federal government should take effective and lawful measures to prevent unlawful killings, particularly those of teachers and students, as well as attacks on schools by Boko Haram and other armed groups in northern Nigeria.
6. The Ministry of education should ensure that re-opened schools are subjected to regular inspection to ensure those standards are being maintained.
7. The international communities should put pressure on the Nigeria authorities to conduct an independent investigation and prosecution of suspected perpetrators of human rights abuses including the abuse of the right to education.

The study is also calling on insurgents (Boko Haram) and other armed groups to cease all unlawful killings, including targeted attacks on teachers, school students and other human right abuses against civilians and immediately stop all attacks on schools and other education facilities

Summary of literature

various studies related to the study were reviewed those study that were similar were critically examine to agree or disagree with the assumption of the present study which attempted to assess the government responses on of the Nigerian government toward counterinsurgency and counterterrorism and its impact on education in northeast Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

Design of the Study

This study employed descriptive survey research design. According to Nworgu (2009) descriptive survey is a study which is aimed at collecting data and describing in a systematic manner, the characteristics, features or facts about given population. Akuezuilo and Agu, (2013) stated that survey design is used in a situation where the study employs questionnaire to determine opinion, preference, attitude and perception of people about an issue. Descriptive survey design is therefore considered appropriate for this study since it sought to assess the impact of Boko Haram on social orientation and academic performance affected secondary schools of Potiskum area of Yobe State.

Simple random sampling was employed for the study which comprises of one hundred and fifty (150) students were randomly selected from five (5) secondary schools in Potiskum local government area of Yobe State.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed in consonance with the review of available literature on the study under investigation. The instrument titled “Impact of Boko Haram on Social Orientation and Academic Performance in affected schools in Potiskum local government area of Yobe State” was developed to elicit information from the respondents. The instrument was structured in a four point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with number values of 4,3,2 and 1 respectively assigned.

Validation of the Instrument

The validity of the instrument for this study was established through face validation. According to Uju (2011), face validation judges at the face value, the appropriateness of the evaluating instrument. There should be no confusing words in the items. Draft copies of the instrument were given to three (3) experts for corrections, comment and advices. The experts were made up of the researchers’ supervisor and two other lecturers from School of Education, Federal College of Education Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua Yobe State..

Method of Data Collection

The questionnaires were administered to the respondents by the researchers. The researchers make to ensure of immediate completion and return of the completed questionnaires by going round to collect the completed questionnaires.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected from the questionnaire items were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. Decision for accepting or rejecting an item or group of items was based on cut-off point of 2.50 therefore, any item greater than or equal to 2.50 was considered agreed while less than or equal to 2.49 were considered disagreed.

PRESENTATION OF THE RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What are the impacts of Boko Haram on social orientation of well-being students in affected secondary school in Potiskum local government area of Yobe State?*

Table 1: Shows the mean and standard deviation on influences of Boko Haram on social well-being of students in secondary schools Potiskum local government area.

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	UD	X	SD	Remarks
1	Crises has an effect on school attendance of both the teachers and students	29	36	14	11	-	3.92	0.99	Agreed
2	Destruction of available facilities in the schools influences the well-being of students in classroom	23	44	0	14	-	3.84	0.98	Agreed
3	Loss of teachers due to the crises in the area influences the well-being of students in classroom	15	44	20	11	-	3.70	0.89	Agreed
4	Damaging school infrastructure can grossly reduce the availability of access to education which reduces performance	17	67	4	2	-	4.10	0.56	Agreed
5	Insurgencies suicide bombings at school as a tactics which in turn reduce school population and affect the academic performance of students	30	43	7	4	6	3.97	1.08	Agreed
6	Destruction of available school facilities by insurgents leaves the educational system in a dire situation	19	27	22	12	10	3.37	1.27	Agreed
7	Insecurity bin the state has been traumatic for students as they are forced to flee their homes in fear	31	31	13	5	10	3.76	1.29	Agreed
8	The attack by the insurgents have leads to the deaths of many students	27	40	13	6	4	3.89	1.05	Agreed
9	Killing and abduction of students by the insurgents induce fear and reduce academic performance	20	48	12	7	3	3.83	0.97	Agreed
10	Violence can affect attendance schools as insecurity constitutes a negative reinforcement due to the obvious fact that teaching and learning cannot successfully occurs in an environment of fear	41	33	10	3	3	4.18	0.99	Agreed

From table 1 above, the findings of the study revealed that all of the respondent agreed with the statements that, crises has an effect on schools attendance of both the teachers and students, destruction of available facilities in the schools influences the well-being of student in classroom, loss of teachers due to the crises in the area influences the well-being of student in classroom, damaging school infrastructure can grossly reduce the availability of access to education which reduces performance, insurgents suicide bombings at school as a tactics which in turn reduce school population and affect the academic performance of students, destruction of available school facilities by insurgents leaves the educational system in a dire situation; insecurity in the state has been traumatic for students as they are forced to flee their homes in tear, the attack by the insurgents have leads to the deaths of many students, killing and abduction of students by the insurgents induce fear and reduce academic performance and violence can affect attendance in schools as insecurity constitutes a negative reinforcement due to the obvious fact that

teaching and learning cannot successfully occurs in an environment of fear are some of the influences of Boko Haram on social well-being of students in secondary schools in Potiskum Local Government Area.

Research Question 2: *What are the impacts of Boko Haram insurgency on the academic performance of students in the study area?*

Table 2: shows the mean and standard deviation on the influences of Boko Haram insurgency on the academic performance of students in the study area

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	UD	X	SD	Remarks
11	Attack on one school/locality leads to fear that any school in the area might be attacked	31	47	3	7	2	4.09	0.94	Agreed
12	Many teachers have been forced to flee for their safety which affect academic performance	35	39	14	1	1	4.18	0.72	Agreed
13	Psychosocial impact of the attacks insurgents affect students ability to learn	24	41	17	6	2	3.88	0.96	Agreed
14	The threat of attacks persists may lead to the students being kept at home which in turn affect their performance	25	43	10	6	6	3.83	1.11	Agreed
15	The targeted attacks at school during insurgencies and the general state of insecurity could force the school to closed	23	46	15	5	3	3.92	0.93	Agreed

From table 2 above, the findings of the study further revealed that all of the respondents also agreed with the statements that, attack on one school/locality leads to fear that any school in the area might be attacked, many teachers have been forced to flee for their safety which affect academic performance, psychosocial impact of the attacks of insurgents affect students ability to learn, threat of attacks persists may lead to the students being kept at home which in turn affect their performance and that the targeted attacks at school during insurgencies and the general state of insecurity could force the school to closed are some of the influence of Boko Haram insurgency on the academic performance of students in the study area.

Research Question 3: *What are proffered ways forward by Government to tackle the attack of Boko Haram in the study area?*

Table 3: shows the means and standard deviation on the proffered ways forward by Government as responses to tackle the attack of Boko Haram in the study area

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	UD	X	SD	Remarks
16	Insurgents (Boko Harams) and other armed groups of cease all unlawful killings, including targeted attacks on teachers, school students	24	44	9	8	5	3.82	1.10	Agreed
17	State government should provide adequate security to prevent attacks on school buildings, teachers and school students/pupils	33	40	10	2	5	4.04	1.04	Agreed
18	Government should renovate all school damaged in the state as a result of them violence and ensure that they are provided with adequate teaching staff	33	37	10	6	4	3.99	1.08	Agreed
19	Federal government on their part should provide adequate support to the affected states by expeditiously rebuild and renovate all school buildings and facilities destroyed during the attacks	22	45	18	3	2	3.91	0.88	Agreed
20	To provide all necessary support to all those including teachers and students, who have been affected by violence which include rehabilitation and resettlement for those who have been forced to flee the violence	28	39	9	10	4	3.85	1.11	Agreed

From table above, the findings of the study also revealed that all of the respondents agreed with the statements that, insurgents (Boko harams) and other armed groups to cease all unlawful killings,

including targeted attacks on teachers, school students, state government should provide government should renovate all schools damaged in the state as a result of them violence and ensure that they are provided with adequate teaching staff, federal government adequate security to prevent attacks on schools buildings, teachers and school, students/pupils, on their part should provide adequate support to the affected stated by expeditiously rebuild and renovate all school building and facilities destroyed during the attacks and ability to provide all necessary support to all those, including teachers and students, who have been affected by violence which include rehabilitation and resettlement for those who have force to flee the violence are some of the ways forward to the impact of Boko Haram towards improving academic performance of students in the study area.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on research question one, the finding of the study revealed that crises has all effect on school attendance of both the teachers and students, destruction of available facilities of the schools influence the well-being of students in classroom; loss of teachers due to the crisis in the area influences the well-being of student in classroom, damaging school infrastructure can grossly reduce the availability of access to education which reduces performance, insurgents suicide bombings at school as a tactics which in turn reduce school population and affect the academic performance of students, destruction of available school facilities by insurgents leaves the educational system in a dire situation, insecurity in the state insurgents have leads to the deaths of many students, killing and abduction of students by the has been traumatic for students as they are forced to flee their homes in fear. Powell, & Abraham (2006). The attack by the insurgents include fear and reduce academic performance and violence can affect attendance and learning cannot successfully occurs in an environment of fear and some of the influences of schools as insecurity constitutes a negative reinforcement due to the obvious fact that Boko Haram insurgents consequently, developed threat on social well-being of students in secondary schools Potiskum local government area of Yobe state.

Based on research question two, the findings of the study also revealed that, attack on one school/locality leads to fear that any school in the area might be attacked, many teachers have been forced to flee for their safety which affect academic performance, psychosocial impact the students being kept at home which in turn affect their performance and that the targeted of the attacks of insurgents affect students ability to learn, threat of attacks persists may lead to attacks at school during insurgencies and the general state of insecurity could force to school to closed and other of the impact of Boko Haram insurgency on the academic performance of students in the study area.

Based on research question three, the findings of the study further revealed that, government did well but more effort should be put in place to tackle insurgents (Boko Haram) and other armed groups to cease all unlawful killings, including targeted attacks on teachers, school students, state government should provide adequate security to prevent attacks on school buildings, teachers and school students/pupils, government should renovate all schools damaged in the state as a result of them violence and ensure that they are provided with adequate teaching staff, federal government on their part should provide adequate support to the affected states by expeditiously rebuild and renovate all school buildings and facilities destroyed during the attacks and ability to provide all necessary support to all those including teachers and students, who have been affected by violence which include rehabilitation and resettlement for those who have been forced to flee the violence are some of the ways forward to the impact of Boko Haram towards improving academic performance of students in the study area.

CONCLUSION

The Boko Haram insurgent by singling out educational institution for concentrated attacks, have killed and maimed several students and teachers, destroyed school buildings and lead to the prolonged closure of schools. This had effect of traumatizing teachers and students while retarding school enrolment and attendance in an area were already poor in education service delivery.

The results of the study provide information for educational psychologists and school counsellors to assist the students to overcome the emotional distress as a result of the adverse effects of insecurity on their academic performance. Teachers' on their part should employ strategies to manage students' emotional distress caused by the insecurity. Through counselling intervention, parents that are not willing to send back their sons and daughters to the affected schools may see the need for them to return their wards to schools or transfer them to other schools that are not affected by the crisis to continue with their studies. Counselling as an intervention strategy may assist an individual adjust well in the society therefore; group counselling for the youths in Nigeria is imperative to help the youth embrace peace and dialogue, because no meaningful development will take place without peace and tranquility. This study exposes to the government and public the devastating nature of insecurity and the danger that is exerting on the education system in the north-east senior secondary schools.

The impact of insecurity on students' academic performance was found to be significant in senior secondary school in Potiskum. This situation if left unchecked, will lead to permanent dropout of many students not only in Potiskum local government area but in the northern part of the country at large thereby making the available for use as political thugs and exposing them to other economic social vices. It is incumbent on the government to provide adequate and effective security personnel to all institution of learning in Yobe state, Nigeria to stop the burning of schools and constant shooting around educational institutions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations have been made:

1. The federal government should post security personnel to guide all schools from primary to tertiary institutions in Nigeria.
2. Effort should be geared towards re-orientation of the masses, especially in the northern part of Nigeria on the importance of education as an instrument for national development.
3. Federal government should adopt policies which lead to creation of jobs to assuage the feelings of disaffected youths who get easily tempted to fight against institutions as a result of their frustrations.
4. Teachers, especially in the northern parts of the country should be given incentives, such as special allowances to continue to compensate them for untold hardship they suffer as a result of Boko Haram insurgency. This will ensure a high rate of retention of teachers in the school system.
5. The federal government should ensure that educational facilities are adequate secured, especially in the northern states, to forestall attacks on the school which claim the lives of students and their teachers alike, while also leading to wanton destruction of school facilities.

REFERENCES

- Abimbiola, M.O and Adosote, S. (2012). Historical Antecedents of Boko Haram insurgency and its implications for sustainable and educational development in north central Nigeria, *Journal of Education and Practice*, Vol. 5, No. 22.
- Abraka N. (2010). Attendance and academic performance of students in secondary schools. A modern approaches. www.krpublishers.com Nigeria
- Abgbiboa, D. (2013) "The Ongoing Campaign of Terror in Nigeria. Boko Haram versus The state" 2 (3) stability: *international journal of security and development*. 1 (1) 234- 241
- Adike, J. (2012). "Boko: One sect, conflicting narratives". African Renaissance, 9 (1) Amenga-Etego R. (eds). *Unraveling and Reweaving the sacred Canon in Africana womanhood (Lexington Books Limhcm 2015)*. 93-106.
- Aminu, A. (2013). School Massacre by insurgent, haunt Nigeria village. *Mail and Guardian* August 13, 2013.
- Amnesty International (2013), "Keep away from schools or we'll kill you", *right to education under attack in Nigeria*, London and amnesty international Ltd.

- Atsua, T.G & Abdullahi G. (2015) “Impact of Boko Haram insurgency on principals, teachers and students in senior secondary schools in Borno State, Nigeria” 2015 knowledge review 1-8
- Aworu, B.E (2015). “Boko Haram insurgency and the underdevelopment of Nigeria” *Research on humanities and social science* 213-220
- Brenda, O. (2010). The long term impact of attacks on education systems, development and fragility and the implications for policy responses. *Education for all Global monitoring report* 2011.
- Danjijibo, F. (2009). Boko Haram in Nigeria: its beginnings, principles and activities in Nigeria, obtained online from www.salafimanhaj.com
- Duku T. (2014). Boko Haram: parents withdraw children from Yobe schools. The nation, Fafunwa A, R (1991) history of education in Nigeria. Ibadan: NPS educational publishers
- Hornby (2008). Oxford Advanced Learners’ Dictionary Oxford: University press
- Oke, R.O & Labeodan H.A (2015), “Boko Haram insurgence, the Chibok Girls’ abduction and the implication for the girl child in Nigeria” in Ross RE and
- Okoro, D. (2014). Boko Haram insurgency and schools closure: food for thought. Retrieved April, 24, 2014 from <http://www.punchng.com/opinion/bokoharam>.
- Ovell, S. (2007). Discipline in schools’ online resource from the Nalanda Institute. <http://nalandainstitute.org/aspfiles/disciplines.asp> accessed 5th February
- Owoeye, J.S & Yara, P.O (2011). “School facilities and academic achievement of Secondary school agricultural science in Ekiti state, Nigeria” 7 (7) *Journal of Asian social science* 64-74.
- Powell, C.H, & Abraham, G. (2006). “Terrorism and international humanitarian law”, *1st African yearbook of international humanitarian law* 118: 127.
- Rogan, G. (2007). Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria as a symptom of poverty and political alienation. *Journal of humanitarian and social sciences*. 3 (5), 21-26.
- Ruiters, A.R (2013) Declining enrolment in primary education in Nigeria. “Press conference, March 11, Abuja: Minister of education.
- Shettu, M. (2000) Islamic education in Nigeria, Ibadan: Spectrum Book Ltd.
- Teboho, M. (2007), “Nigeria education sector analysis – An analytical synthesis of performance and main issues” – world Bank document, 52 p.
- The daily review newspapers (2015, October, 12) Buhari releases N56 billion to rebuild Areas destroyed by Boko Haram, dailyreviewonline.com.ng/2015/10/12/buharireleasessn56billion-to-revuild-areas-destroyed-by-boko-haram.
- Ugwumba, E.U & Odom, T.C (2014) Boko Haram insurgency: a Peril to Achievement of education for all in Nigeria, *international journal of education learning and development*, Vol. 3, No. 1 pp 1-11.
- Uju, A.E (2000). Guide to writing research project report in tertiary institution. Enugu: John Jacob’s publishers.
- Umar B & Manabete, S.S (2015) “peace and security: Challenges to education and communal existence in Nigeria” in Dichaba M and Nwaozuzu D (eds) *Rethinking teaching and learning in the 21st century* (African academic research forum arcadia Umar, H. (2013). 27 students killed in northwest Nigeria. Associated press October 2, 2013. United Nations Educational, Scientific and cultural organization (2010).
- Uzodike, L. & Maingwa, D. (2012). Boko Haram and the kidnapping of the Chibok School girls. *CTC Sentinel*, 7 (5), 1-8.<https://www.ctc.usma.edu/posts/boko-haram-aid1d-the-kidnapping-of-the-chiboks-schools-girls>.
- Vanguard, (2013) “Will there be peace in our time? *The Vanguard*, Wednesday, September 28 P 36.